

SMM as a Tool to Promote Products and Services in the Modern Economy through the Internet

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the concept of SMM as a tool for promotion and marketing of goods and services in the economy to the market. It also highlighted the main advantages and disadvantages of SMM - promotion. Described the specifics, trends and conduct and promotion in social networks. The definition of concepts such as brand, targeting, target audience. Considered the dynamics of SMM tools and current trends in the industry. Highlighted the features and importance of the target audience for brand promotion. What we have to consider when creating content, choosing methods of community-building, tools for promotion.

KEYWORDS: SMM, internet, marketing, social networks, brand, economy, promotion, market, demand, targeting, target audience.

INTRODUCTION

Today the concept of SMM (Social Media Marketing) is gaining momentum and popularity. Social networks, the Internet are very actively penetrating into our lives, sometimes taking away our free time. If 10 years ago the Internet was not so popular, now in every home we have the Internet, without which we can no longer imagine our lives. We are used to choosing, researching and buying everything we want and everything that interests us. It follows that companies selling their products and services need to keep up with the times and take into account that potential customers are in the vast Internet. In order to deserve the attention of potential customer, you need to meet today's demands.

Every day, according to statistics, a person accesses social media at least once, a figure that is gaining momentum with each passing day. This is becoming a very good opportunity for companies to "befriend" their potential customers. Therefore, today, it is very important and very necessary for selling companies to be present in social networks. At the moment there are a lot of competing companies, which indicates healthy competition, so it is more difficult to persuade people to buy, to talk to them, to please them. And when people are on social media they are in their comfort zone. For this reason, it is important to consider all opportunities to promote products and services.

MAIN PART

SMM Social Media Marketing is a method of work in social media, which appeared recently in the mid-2000s.

Konstantin Maksimyuk, the founder of New Internet, interprets SMM as "marketing in social networks", essentially synonymous to "work in social networks", although with a focus on product and service promotion.

Internet portal perfectseo.ru says about social media: "SMM is a new but very promising way to promote products and services using forums, blogosphere, social networks, instant messaging, that is, all the social media channels available today. It appeared on the marketing market just 7 years ago, and has managed to prove its high effectiveness. » (1)

Others talk about SMM as a process of attracting traffic or attention to a brand or product through social platforms. It is a set of activities that use social media as channels to promote companies and other business objectives.

The main features of SMM promotion are:

1. Communication with the target audience;
2. Audience statistics (activity) in real time;
3. Daily contact with the target audience;

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4. Advertising at relatively low cost of promotion (customer feedback on the brand) if the campaign is successful;
5. Efficiency;
6. Wide coverage of the target audience;
7. Constant posting in the feed;
8. Use of targeted advertising;
9. Ability to use non-standard formats;
10. Event marketing;

Initially, no one took SMM seriously, everyone started their own blog, writing about sellers, about the product, leaving links, contacts of sellers, craftsmen, etc. Shared about a good product they bought or a quality service they received. All this was informal and the bloggers' remuneration was token. The real activity of SMM started with the development of social media, when the number of users began to exceed six zeros, the marketing market grew. Accordingly, the demand for SMM agencies and freelancers began to increase. For advertisers, it was a great opportunity to maximize exposure to their specific target audience and also to accelerate the promotion of a new or existing brand.

The main methods of SMM promotion are:

1. Work with on-site advertising through thematic resources, where there is an opportunity to link to a blog, forum, social page;
2. Opportunity to create a thematic publicity in social networks to attract potential customers to go to the promoted site;
3. Creation of provocative and striking headlines that will attract the attention of network users to visit the promoted website;
4. Recruitment and purchase of bots, likes in social networks to attract the attention of users to the content;

All these methods also have different subgroups, they can be improved and include new exclusive methods and strategies, but the main purpose of SMM promotion remains the same - to create a good reputation for the product, company, attracting new target audience and its recognition of the product, goods or services.

It is also important to consider the advantages and disadvantages of SMM promotion.

Starting with the advantages, the advantages of SMM promotion include:

1. The cost, it is small, you can say low, unlike other services. In order to create a specific group, to increase the number of friends does not require a large expenditure, which is very attractive to business promotion. The main costs, it is the cost in time for the collection, processing and presentation of the necessary information;
2. High virility effect. If the posted material is unusual, aggressive, interesting, creative, it can gather a large audience of potential customers. His friends will see him, share this material with others, etc., and after a while the material will be seen by thousands of people. This creates a viral effect;
3. Development perspective. The number of users in social networks is increasing by the minute;
4. Low competition. Large companies are not yet investing heavily in social platforms. Consequently, with The expected impact on your business can be achieved for a small amount of money;

The disadvantages of SMM promotion include:

1. Lack of information in analytics. Today, it is very difficult to know and analyses the actions of visitors on a social page. It is difficult to find out from where and from what services they learned and passed on the link on the page;
2. Control by network moderators. It is easy to get blacklisted and spammed for excessive network activity. Because of this fear, the company loses the subscribers it has gained. Therefore, it is necessary to know the rules of social networks well in order not to face such a situation.
3. The presence of a promoted brand. If an untwisted brand is already in the limelight, it is easier to reach potential customers through it, and vice versa. An unfamiliar brand requires more effort to attract the attention of the audience;
4. The need for administration. A lot of attention and time needs to be given to support, especially if there are thousands of subscribers. For this you need to hire a separate person for the position of administrator;

As we know, social media has and is gaining more and more popularity among people all over the world. This is due to the fact that people like and are comfortable to communicate and get a lot of information. Huge platforms like Instagram, Facebook, Vkontakte are great for advertising. Every year, social media platforms are expanding and evolving.

To successfully use social media promotion, you need to do the following things;

1. Be active in social networks, to be visible in simple words;
2. Create your own website. With the help of the website it is easier and faster to convey information to potential consumers;

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3. Using social networking buttons on the site, i.e. it is necessary to organize data exchange between the site and social networks;

Consider the trends highlighted by Natalia Ermolova, author of the textbook "Business promotion in social networks Facebook, Twitter, Google +", which are used to create content and promote brands in social networks.

1. Unique content - strategy - the largest communities rely primarily on uniqueness as well as visual content when forming a content strategy;

2. Popularity of video content;

3. Unique content "behind the scenes" - one of the trends in constructing a content marketing policy of the brand is generation of content showing how the product is made, what company produced it, what principles it follows when creating the product. This can be photo and video materials from production, interviews with employees, etc;

4. Opinion of experts. Involvement of experts, opinion leaders interesting to the audience, celebrities and all those who can generate unique content "playing on brand territory";

5. Emphasis on product. Creating unique product photo and video content;

6. Non-standard content formats. Wiki markup, coub, gif - looped short videos, non-standard communication mechanics (quests, etc.);

7. Personalized communication;

8. Event-driven marketing;

Social media has advantages over other mechanisms of the online marketing system. Brand recognition, contact with the audience, increased sales - all these objectives can be achieved by a social media presence. But the main advantage is targeting - focusing an advertising campaign on a particular segment of the target audience. As statistics show, most users have long since passed registration in social networks and provided full information about themselves when registering. As a result, the SMM specialist has a huge amount of information to select the target audience for the company. (3)

1. "Word of mouth». users tend to share useful information and this is very developed in social networks; (4)

2. Unadvertised format. The Internet is one of the aggressive mediums, in terms of advertising. Many people do not pay attention when entering a website to pop-up advertisements. SMM does not use an advertising format. The main methods of contact and interaction with the audience are communication on relevant topics, dissemination of useful information; (5)

3. Interactive interaction. In social networks, potential customers, i.e. users can exchange information, participate in polls and discussions, and ask different questions. That is, the seller has a feedback with the buyer. Today, most companies have a page in various social networks. This fact shows the need for promotion on Internet sites;

It is worth noting that it is necessary to take into account some specific points in the SMM promotion:

- The presentation of information should be as concise as possible, interesting, attractive;

- Should be all bright to attract attention;

- Stimulate discussion;

- Creating a positive reputation and image of the company;

- Constant updating of information in the group, the optimal placement of posts per day one to five;

- Attracting target audience, timely information;

- Targeting advertising - advertising in social networks in search of the target audience;

The following is a sample step-by-step plan with which to develop your individual brand promotion strategy:

1. Define your target audience;

2. Identifying your company's key objectives; (6)

3. Selecting sites with a high target audience;

4. Defining the daily behavior of the audience, i.e. passive users, active participants, content generators;

5. Developing a content plan; (7)

6. Selection of performance indicators, i.e. audience reach, activity patterns, traffic, sales;

7. Identification of the resources needed;

8. Development of an annual plan;

9. Evaluating the effectiveness and adjustments of the company;

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research we can see that SMM promotion is one of the topical directions in the industry of modern economy. Today social networks are developing very rapidly, which requires special attention to promote products and services through social networks. We found that the definition of CA (target audience) is very important as CA is the potential customers with

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whom it is appropriate to build credible communication. We can safely say that SMM promotion is a very important tool in the marketing system.

REFERENCES

- 1) Ambler. T. Practical Marketing / T. Ambler - SPb: Peter 2000.-213 p;
- 2) Antonov L.V. Peculiarities of entrepreneurial activity at the advertising market. // Socio-economic phenomena and processes / L.V. Antonov 20011, № 8, pp. 9-12;
- 3) Afanasyev V.T. Social information - M., 2011. -120 c;
- 4) Bagiev G.L. Marketing: textbook for universities / V.M. Tarasevich, H. Ann, G.L. Bagiev - SPb Peter 2007 - 736 pp;
- 5) Baklanova Yu.O. The evolution of the approach to project management innovation: the initiative, project, program, portfolio. Yu.O. Baklanova // Modern Management Technologies. - 2012 - №3. Article number: 1501;
- 6) F. Kotler Fundamentals of Marketing / F. Kotler, G. Armstrong, D. Saunders. - M. Publishing house "Williams", 2008 - 300 p;
- 7) Marketing. General Course: Textbook / Edited by N.Ya. Omega-L, 2007 - 795 pp;
- 8) Science and innovation. No 19. Page 59;
- 9) <http://sendpulse.com/blog/smm-tools>;
- 10) <http://esj.today/issue-2-2019.html>;
- 11) Amirova D.R. Advantages of using Internet marketing tools for modern companies // Economics and Business: Theory and Practice. - 2018 No.2 page 14-17;